

Impact Of Covid 19 Lockdown On Career Choice Of Some Selected Private School Teachers In Lagos State, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

The incidence of covid – 19 pandemic rudely affected the walls of many nations in the world bringing to an halt all activities of nations in the years 2020. The educational sector is inevitably the mostly affected as teachers and students were compelled to sit at home without any objection as a result of the health risk attached. It is on this premise that the current study appraises the impact covid -19 lockdown has on the career choice of some selected private school teachers in Lagos State, Nigeria with focus on motivation and knowledge of ICT among the teachers. A descriptive research design was employed, 73 respondents attended to the online survey on COVID – 19 and career choice of teachers (CCCT) comprising of fifteen items which were administered to private school teachers. The data collected were analysed using the descriptive and inferential method where frequency tables and percentages were displayed also the Pearson Product Moment Correlation were used to test the two hypotheses stated. Findings of the first hypothesis was rejected where it reveals that an average statistical relationship exists between motivation by private school owners during covid -19 pandemic lockdown and career choice of teachers. Hypothesis two was also rejected and it reveals that an average statistical relationship exists between knowledge of ICT among the teachers during covid -19 pandemic lockdown and their choice of career. The study however, recommended regular ICT training for teachers, granting of soft loans and employment of different motivation strategies to teachers for competencies to be gained while discharging their duties.

Keywords: covid – 19, motivation, ICT knowledge, career choice

INTRODUCTION

The COVID-19 pandemic affected people regardless of nationality, level of education, income or gender. But the same has not been true for its consequences, which have hit the most vulnerable hardest. Education is no exception. Students from privileged backgrounds, supported by their parents are eager and able to learn, they could find their way past closed school doors to alternative learning opportunities. Those from disadvantaged backgrounds often remained shut out when their schools shut down. This crisis has exposed the many inadequacies and inequalities in our education systems – from access to the broadband and computers needed for online education, and the supportive environments needed to focus on learning, up to the misalignment between resources and needs. The COVID-19 pandemic and eventual lockdown has affected educational systems worldwide, leading to the near-total closures of schools, universities and colleges. According to UNESCO monitoring, over 130 countries implemented

nationwide closures, impacting over 80% of world's student population. Several other countries implemented localized school closures subjecting millions of learners to education disruption.

Most governments around the world decided to temporarily close educational institutions in an attempt to reduce the spread of COVID-19. School closures impact not only students, teachers, and families but have far-reaching economic and societal consequences. School closures in response to the pandemic have exposed various social and economic issues, including student debt, digital learning, food insecurity, and homelessness, as well as access to childcare, health care, housing, internet, and disability services.

On 20th March 2020, the Federal Government of Nigeria directed all schools to close immediately as a precautionary step aimed at preventing the spread of COVID-19 which has become a global threat. While some schools were done with their second term examinations, some were yet to complete the term. While the majority of high fee-paying schools moved to online learning, the greater part of learners from poor and low-income homes were at a disadvantage as they had limited or no access to alternative learning platforms provided by the government.

Adeosun (2010), emphasized that some state governments had come up with policies and programs to arouse teachers and students' interest in ICT but the initiatives were short term, piloted and donor-funded projects as such it wasn't sustained. This can be related to the fact that infrastructure on digital learning in Nigeria generally has not been developed significantly to cope with the current trend of teaching to learning with ICT basically because Nigeria is still one of the developing countries in the world.

According to Studi Economici Dell'Ocse (OECD) studies, school performance hinges critically on maintaining close relationships with teachers. This is particularly true for students from disadvantaged backgrounds, who may not have the parental support needed to learn on their own. Working parents are more likely to miss work when schools close in order to take care of their children, incurring wage loss in many instances and negatively impacting productivity. The global lockdown of education institutions caused major (and likely unequal) interruption in students' learning; disruptions in internal assessments; and the cancellation of public assessments for qualifications or their replacement by an inferior alternative. Going to school is the best public policy tool available to raise skills. While school time can be fun and can raise social skills and social awareness, from an economic point of view the primary point of being in school is that it increases a child's ability. Even a relatively short time in school does this; thus even a relatively short period of missed school will have consequences for skill growth.

The impact of the pandemic alone has led to speculation regarding impacts to the teaching profession (De La Rosa, 2020). Some educators lost their jobs because of non-sustainability of some educational institutions during the pandemic. Education scholars and polls suggest shifting trends such as: decreased enrollment in educator preparation programs, decreased teacher interest in staying in the profession, and increased considerations for retirement (Kurtz & Bushweller, 2020; Lardieri, 2020; Perry, 2020). Laying off teachers "is an emotionally fraught and demoralizing process for a community. Layoffs often result in significantly lower academic outcomes" (Burnette & Will, 2020). Empirical research shows that a seniority-based approach to determining layoffs is not the best approach, especially because the impact will likely disproportionately affect high poverty and high-minority schools (Goldhaber & Theobald, 2020). Reduced education budgets and subsequent teacher layoffs will likely disproportionately impact disadvantaged schools and the teachers who teach specifically in low-performing schools. Research suggests that the mere threat of layoffs or potential loss of future compensation may cause teachers to leave the profession altogether (Goldhaber, 2013)

Research shows that most teachers enter and stay in the profession due to a motivation to work with children (Watt & Richardson, 2007). Schools adapted to the process of remote teaching – learning which is usually facilitated online through the use of technology. This was as a result of the dramatic changes COVID – 19 brought in the way we live our lives which impacted students and teachers worldwide Mailizar et al. (2020). Information and communications technology is a term generally used to refer to the convergence of audiovisual broadcast systems, telephones, and computer networks through a single cabling or linking system (Chan & Holosko, 2016). In the work of Michael W. L. et al. (2023), on the experience of social work educators on the use of technology during covid – 19, their results indicated

that social work educators must adapt, be creative, engage student voices, and innovate by testing and evaluating different pedagogies and even their applicability with various technological tools.

Statement of the problem

COVID-19 has brought about changes to the education system that impact teachers in multiple ways. The current economic downturn due to Covid 19 lockdown has put a large number of private school teachers' jobs at risk. The COVID-19 pandemic has affected educational systems worldwide, leading to the near-total closures of schools, universities and colleges. Going to school is the best public policy tool available to raise skills. While school time can be fun and can raise social skills and social awareness, from an economic point of view the primary point of being in school is that it increases a child's ability. Majority of the teachers during the COVID-19 pandemic lockdown struggled from adopting the new normal way of teaching which brought about the usage of information and communication technology via different platforms. Some teachers also lost their jobs while others willingly left the profession. The issue of motivation was also a point of concern during the lockdown.

Purpose of the study

The broad objective of this study seeks to find out the impact of Covid 19 lockdown on career choice of some selected private school teachers in Lagos state, Nigeria.

The specific objectives are;

1. To determine if motivation by the school owners during covid 19 lockdown has relationship with career choice of teachers.
2. To determine if knowledge of ICT during covid 19 lockdown has relationship with career choice of teachers.

Research Questions

1. Does motivation by the school owners during covid 19 lockdown has relationship with the career choice of teachers?
2. Does the knowledge of ICT during covid 19 lockdown has relationship with the career choice of teachers?

Research Hypotheses

1. Significant relationship does not exist between motivation by school owners during covid 19 pandemic and career choice of teachers.
2. Significant relationship does not exist between knowledge of ICT during covid 19 pandemic and career choice of teachers.

RESEARCH METHOD

The research design for this study is a descriptive survey research design. A total number of 73 teachers from some selected private schools participated in the study. Self-structured questionnaire was employed to collect data from the respondents

DATA PRESENTATION ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

This section presents the analyses of the data and the interpretation of results based on the research hypotheses stated. The descriptive and inferential statistical tool was used in this work. Data collected from the administered questionnaire are analysed using the statistical package for social science to carry out the correlation analysis for the two hypotheses stated. Interpretations are therefore made accordingly based on the results generated.

Table 1: Demographic Characteristics Of The Respondents

N = 73

VARIABLE	CATEGORIES	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
GENDER	Male	19	26
	Female	54	74
AGE	21 – 40	39	53.4
	41 – 60	34	46.6
MARITAL STATUS	Single	22	30.1
	Married	49	67.1
	Divorced	0	0
	Widowed	2	2.8
TYPE OF ESTABLISHMENT	Low Income Level School	15	20.5
	Middle Income Level School	35	47.9
	High Income Level School	23	31.5
SCHOOL FEES PER TERM	#15,000 - #20,000	11	15.1
	#21,000 - #50,000	8	11
	#51,000 - 100,000	5	7
	#100,000 and above	49	67.1
NUMBER OF PUPILS IN SCHOOL	Below 25 students	9	12.3
	30 - 50 students	6	8.3
	55 - 100 students	6	8.2
	Above 100 students	10	13.7
	Above 200 students	42	57.5

The evidence from table above reveals that a total of 54 representing (74%) of the respondents are females while the male respondents accounted for 19(26%) of the total participants. For the age distribution of the respondents. Those within the age bracket of 21 – 40 has the highest number of 39 with a total of 53.4%, followed by respondents that fall within the age range of 41 – 60 having (34)46.6%. Respondents within 21 – 40 has the lowest number of respondents with 39(53.4%). The table also reveals that the marital status of the respondents where 49(67.1%) of them are married followed by 22(30.1%) that are singles, only 2(2.8%) are widowed while none of the respondents are divorced. The type of establishment respondents work was also revealed, where 35(47.9%) work in a middle-income level school, 23(31.5%) work in a high-income level school, while only 15(20.5%) work in a low-income level school. The school fees paid per term in each of these schools varies 49(67.1%) agreed that their pupils paid between #100,000 and above, 11(15.1%) agreed that #15,000 - #20,000 are paid while 8 respondents with 11% noted that #21,000 - #50,000 are paid, but only 5(7%) agreed that #51,000 - #100,000 are paid. Still on the same vein, the number of pupils in the schools according to the respondents was also attended to where 42(57.5%) agreed that they have more than 200 students in their school, 10(13.7%) revealed that they have between 100 to two hundred students in their school, while 6(8.3%) respondents agreed that they have between 30 to 50 students and 55 to 100 students respectively.

SECTION B:

Responses on the Impacts covid-19 had on the respondents.

N = 73

VARIABLE	CATEGORIES	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
My school was able to continue offering services during the pandemic	SA	30	41.1
	A	26	35.6
	D	6	8.2
	SD	11	15.1
My school responded to the pandemic by migrating our services effectively online	SA	30	41.1
	A	24	32.9
	D	7	9.6
	SD	12	16.4
My school was not able to migrate our services effectively online.	SA	7	9.6
	A	11	15.1
	D	17	23.3
	SD	38	52.1
My school lost appreciable income during the lockdown	SA	17	23.3
	A	45	1.6
	D	3	4
	SD	8	11
My school was not able to meet the financial obligations of staff salaries during the lockdown.	SA	18	24.7
	A	36	49.3
	D	12	16.4
	SD	7	9.6
My school was not able to function anymore after the lockdown and I had to look for other employment	SA	4	5.2
	A	2	3.1
	D	25	34.2
	SD	42	57.5
Teachers in my school already sought other employment and did not resume when schools resumed.	SA	4	5.5
	A	10	13.7
	D	23	31.5
	SD	36	49.3
The students did not resume after the lockdown, so the school had to retrench staff.	SA	2	3.1
	A	4	5.1
	D	26	35.6
	SD	41	56.2
As a result of my loss of income and hardship, I am considering moving into another profession.	SA	4	5.5
	A	11	15.1
	D	32	43.8

	SD	26	35.6
With the hardship experienced during Covid-19 lockdown, teaching is no longer a viable profession. I have opted out already.	SA	3	4.3
	A	8	11
	D	35	47.9
	SD	27	37
I can never allow my children or anyone I know to choose teaching as a career because of my experience.	SA	5	6.8
	A	5	6.8
	D	46	63
	SD	17	23.3
The lockdown exposed the finding issues existent in private school education in Nigeria.	SA	13	17.8
	A	47	64.4
	D	4	5.5
	SD	9	12.3
Teacher training should include practical technology usage as a teaching skill.	SA	11	15.1
	A	26	35.6
	D	6	8.2
	SD	30	41.1
My school paid this percentage of salary during the lockdown.	Full Salary	6	8.5
	Half Salary	4	5.2
	Quarter/25%	47	64.4
	Nothing		21.9
The following people should create emergency funds for private schools to alleviate the hardships in unforeseen circumstances such as the pandemic.	Banks	29	39.7
	Federal Government	63	86.3
	School Owners	35	47.9
	Non-governmental organization	1	1.4
	Telecoms because of the use of data	1	1.4
	State government	1	1.4
	NGO's	1	1.4
	Investors	1	1.4
	132	181	

Above are the responses of the respondents on the impact covid – 19 had on them in their various schools. 30(41.1%) strongly agreed that their school was able to continue offering services during the pandemic, 26(35.6%) agreed to the statement, 11(15.1%) strongly disagreed, while only 6(8.2%) disagreed. This therefore implies that services were still carried out among majority of the schools of respondents. For majority of the respondents with 30(41.1%) services were promptly migrated online in order to respond to the pandemic, 24(32.9%) of the respondents agreed to the statements while very far to it were respondents with 12(16.4%) and 7(9.6%) who strongly disagreed and disagreed respectively to the fact that their services were migrated online during the era of the pandemic. On the other way round, 38(52.1%) of the

respondents strongly disagreed to the statement that their school was not able to migrate services effectively online, while far to this was respondents who disagreed, agreed and strongly agreed respectively with frequency counts of 17(23.3%), 11(15.1%) and 7(9.6%).

During the lockdown, large percentage of the respondents with 45(61.6%) agreed to the Fact that their school lost appreciable income, while 17(23.3%), 8(11%) and 3(4%) strongly agreed, strongly disagreed and disagreed respectively to the fact that their school lost large income during the lockdown. Similarly, 36(49.3%) of the respondents agreed that their school was not able to meet the financial obligations of staff salaries during the lockdown, 18(24.7%) strongly agreed to inability of school to meet financial obligations of staff salaries, 12(16.4%) disagreed to the statement while only 7(9.6%) disagreed to the statement. As such, majority of the respondents obliged to the fact that their school was unable to meetup financial obligations of teachers during the lockdown.

42(57.5%) of the respondents strongly disagreed to the fact that they had to go in search of other work because of non-functionality of their school after lockdown, 25(34.2%) disagreed on the statement while the choices of strongly agreed and agreed were 4(5.2%) and 2(3.1%) respectively. Most of the respondents 36(49.3%) strongly disagreed with the statement that majority of the teachers in their school already sought other employment and did not resume when school resumed, 23(31.5%) disagreed to the statement while 10(13.7%) and 4(5.5%) agreed and strongly agreed to the statement. Basically, majority of the respondents did not support to the statements that most teachers in their school sought other employment and did not resume when schools resumed. Still in the same vein, 41(56.2%) strongly disagreed with the statement that students did not resume after the lockdown leading to the retrenchment of staff, 26(35.6%) disagreed, while only 4(5.1%) and 2(3.1%) agreed and strongly agreed with the statement.

As a result of loss of income and hardship, 32(43.8%) of the respondents strongly disagreed to the fact that they are considering moving into another profession closer to it are respondents who disagreed to the item while 11(15.1%) and 4(5.5%) agreed and strongly agreed to the fact that they are considering moving into another profession due to loss of income and hardship. With lot of hardship experienced during covid 19 lockdown, 35(47.9%) disagreed to the fact that teaching is no longer a viable profession, 27(37%) strongly disagreed while 8(11%) and 3(4.3%) agreed and strongly agreed to switching into another job as a result of hardship and loss of income.

Among all the respondents in this study, a whole of 46(63%) concluded that they disagreed to the statement when asked if they can never allow their children or anyone to choose teaching as a profession, 17(23.3%) strongly disagreed while 5(6.8%) choose strongly agreed and agreed respectively on the statement.

47(64.4%) agreed that the lockdown has exposed issues existent in private school education in Nigeria. The respondents that strongly agreed with it were 13(17.8%) while 9(12.3%) strongly disagreed and 4(5.5) disagreed to the statement that issues in private school education was exposed during the lockdown. On the inclusion of practical technology usage during teacher training, 30(41.1%) strongly disagreed to the statement. 26(35.6%) of the respondents agreed to the statement while 11(15.1%) and 6(8.2%) strongly agreed and disagreed respectively to the inclusion of practical technology during teacher training.

Also, from the table, 47(64.4%) of the respondents noted that quarter/25% of their salary was paid during the lockdown, 16(21.9%) revealed that nothing was paid to them while only 6(8.5%) and 4(5.2%) said they were paid full salary and half salary respectively during the lockdown.

However, among one hundred and thirty-two (132) respondents, a large number 63(86.3%) noted that the federal government needs to create emergency funds for private schools to alleviate the hardships in unforeseen circumstances such as the pandemic, 35 (47.9%) noted that private school owners should alleviate such hardship in future similar situation, 29(39.7%) also believed that banks are responsible for creating emergency funds during any future occurrence , while other respondents 1(1.4%) believed that nongovernmental organization, telecoms, state government, NGOs and investors should come to the rescue in future occurrence to alleviate hardships in unforeseen circumstances such as the pandemic.

ANALYSIS OF HYPOTHESES

Significant relationship does not exist between motivation by school owners during covid 19 pandemic and career choice of teachers.

Table 3: PPMC on the relationship between motivation by school owners during covid 19 pandemic and career choice of teachers.

Variables	Number N	Mean X	Standard Deviation SD	r	Sig.p	Remark
MOTIVATION	73	9.78	2.99	.568	.004	Significant
CAREER CHOICE OF TEACHERS	73	11.42	2.89			

Evidence from the table above reveals that the r calculated of 0.568 implies that there is an average relationship between motivation by private school owners during covid -19 pandemic lockdown and career choice of teachers. This is however, significant at 5% level of significance with a p-value of .004 ($p < 0.05$). It therefore shows that an average statistical relationship exists between motivation by private school owners during covid -19 pandemic lockdown and career choice of teachers. The null hypothesis stated is therefore rejected.

Significant relationship does not exist between knowledge of ICT during covid 19 pandemic and career choice of teachers.

Table 4: PPMC on the relationship between Knowledge of ICT during covid 19 pandemic and career choice of teachers

Variables	Number N	Mean X	Standard Deviation SD	r	Sig.p	Remark
KNOWLEDGE OF ICT	73	10.53	2.97	.409	.000	Significant
CAREER CHOICE OF TEACHERS	73	11.42	2.89			

Evidence from the table above reveals that the r calculated of 0.409 implies that there is an average relationship between the knowledge of ICT during covid 19 pandemic and career choice of teachers. This is however, significant at 5% level of significance ($p < 0.05$). It is therefore evident that an average statistical relationship exists between knowledge of ICT during covid -19 pandemic lockdown and career choice of teachers. The null hypothesis stated is therefore rejected.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The findings of hypothesis one was rejected. It showed that an average statistical relationship exists between motivation by private school owners during covid -19 pandemic lockdown and career choice of teachers. This result is related with the work of Kurtz & Bushweller, 2020; Lardieri, 2020; Perry, (2020) where their work on education scholars and polls suggests shifting trends, decreased enrollment in educator preparation programs, decreased teacher interest in staying in the profession, and increased considerations for retirement. The work of researchers such as Watt & Richardson, (2007) also support the findings of this studies where it was affirmed that majority of the teachers stayed in the teaching profession due to the passion and motivation they derive working with children.

The second hypothesis was also rejected, it revealed that an average statistical relationship exists between knowledge of ICT during covid -19 pandemic lockdown and career choice of teachers. The findings here is coherent with what Mailizar et al. (2020) asserted. They affirmed that the dramatic changes covid 19 brought has affected teachers and learners' way of life worldwide by way of using remote teaching –

learning process which is usually facilitated through the use of technology. The work of Michael W. L. et al. (2022) for social work education on information communication technology during covid 19 also relates with the findings of this current study where it was confirmed that the knowledge of ICT is important as such social work educators should adapt, be creative, engage student voices, and innovate by testing and evaluating different pedagogies and even their applicability with various technological tools. They however, noted that social work educators should advocate for an international digital equality.

CONCLUSIONS

The rude way in which covid 19 broke the walls of all nations in the world was such an eye opener to all industries especially the educational sector where the consumers (learners) and suppliers (teachers) of educational information in the four walls of schools are mostly affected. This however, brought about this research topic which ponders on the impact of covid 19 lockdown on career choice of some selected private school teachers in Lagos state, Nigeria. Two indices of career choice was critically examined; motivation and knowledge of ICT where the motivation of teachers by the school owners and administrators during the pandemic was actually put to test.

Covid 19 was also noted to have challenged the knowledge of teachers in ICT and pedagogical process of teaching to learning through the introduction of remote teaching technologies in schools. This current study therefore concluded that Nigeria being a developing country was highly affected as other advanced countries adapted the usage of information and communication technologies to conduct classroom teaching and practice instructions almost seamlessly to combat the challenges.

This current study however supports the views of previous researchers to affirm that online teaching and learning will undoubtedly remain far beyond covid-19 which will definitely impact the curriculum of schools at all levels. There is thus a great need to look into the challenges and ensure such are mitigated before a similar challenge occurs.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The uncertainty created by covid 19 in the year 2019 is certainly affecting how we prepare for future teachers at all levels of education. The following recommendations are however proposed to all stakeholders.

1. All teachers at different levels of education should be ready to embrace the positive change covid – 19 pandemics brought into the school curriculum.
2. Private school administrators should endeavor to motivate their teachers adequately so as to reduce the regular turnover of teachers.
3. Learners at all levels of education should be ready to adjust to the usage of ICT for learning as a major teaching tool so as to be included as the world has changed technologically.
4. Regular training programs for teachers in public and private schools should be instituted by the state government.
5. Parents are also required to provide an enabling environment for their children/wards to participate actively in all forms of online learning they are exposed to.
6. Lagos state government and private school administrators should encourage all teachers to own a personal computer and other information and communication technology gadgets by granting soft loans to the teachers. This will however, enable them gain competences that are required to discharge their duties effectively in this post pandemic era.
7. It is of utmost importance that the use of current technology is mainstreamed into teacher education for easy adaptability to the speed of advancement in learnings and teaching methods.

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